

AI Adoption & Governance Self-Assessment Brochure

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Zsolt Almási¹, Jolanta Pietrkiewicz-Knecht², Henry Encabo³, Jason Occidental⁴

¹ Pázmány Péter Catholic University, Hungary
almasi.zsolt@btk.ppke.hu

² Law Office of a Legal Counsel
j.pietrkiewicz@knecht.pl

³ University of Southeastern Philippines, Philippines
hcencabo@usep.edu.ph

⁴ Ateneo de Davao University, Philippines
jtoccidental@addu.edu.ph

1. General Information

This brochure is based on our article “Developing Artificial Intelligence Governance in Higher Education: Ethical and Regulatory Lacunae, and Cross-Cultural Challenges” (TBP). This brochure is designed to help universities and higher education institutions conduct a structured self-assessment of AI-related use, ethical readiness, and policy development. It is aimed at fostering responsible and reflexive use of AI. Specifically, it will be useful for

- Identifying and mapping AI use across your institution
- Highlighting ethical, regulatory, and cultural gaps
- Supporting cross-cultural and cross-jurisdictional collaboration
- Fostering a culture of relational ethics, symbiotic agency, and ethical reflexivity

Check each box if the statement applies to your institution.

2. Identification of AI Use

Are you using AI for the following administrative purposes?

- Supporting university administration (attendance tracking, course reporting, room scheduling)
- Automatically generating reports
- Automatic transcription of meetings
- Analysis of general university data for strategic planning
- IT support and helpdesk automation

Are you using AI for teaching and learning?

- Educational chatbots or virtual assistants helping students with home assignments or projects
- Generating educational materials (notes, summaries, quizzes, flashcards)
- Recommending courses, learning paths, or reading materials based on student activity

- Virtual labs, simulations, or interactive exercises (without grading)
- Personalized learning content in e-learning platforms (e.g., adjusting difficulty)
- Automatic grading of tests, exams, or written assignments
- Monitoring students during exams (proctoring, video/audio analysis)

Are you using AI for student and teaching staff support?

- Supporting decisions on admissions, scholarships, or other educational resources
- Predictive analytics to identify students at risk of attrition or dropping out
- Managing and personalizing institutional communications with students.
- Supporting faculty performance evaluations using student-related data

3. Thematic Self-Assesment

In this section, identify whether the statement is true to your institution's AI policies and practices.

Theme 1: Ethical Responsibility & Otherness of AI

- Requires reflection on how AI shaped thinking, not just disclosure
- Encourages structured opportunities to articulate AI's influence
- Addresses psychological, relational, or societal harms
- Frames responsibility for AI use as collective/institutional, not just individual

Theme 2: Symbiotic Human-AI Relations

- Assessments criteria require demonstration of AI collaboration
- AI is treated as a co-creative partner in teaching/research
- Pedagogical experimentation with AI is encouraged/supported
- Training programs teach "working with AI," not just "using AI"

Theme 3: Ethical Reflexivity

- Regular mechanisms (workshops, committees) are in place to examine AI's impact
- Users are required to assess AI outputs for bias, silencing or epistemic limitations
- Reflexivity is embedded in assessment criteria and practices
- Critical AI literacy is supported beyond procedural rules

Theme 4: Cross-cultural & Regulatory Lacunae

- Guidance is provided for cross-border AI projects
- Policy includes mapping to various regulatory frameworks (EU AI Act, UNESCO, ASEAN Guide)
- Addresses unequal access to AI tools (paid vs. free, accessibility)
- International students/staff & partners are consulted in policy development
- Consideration of cultural, ethical, and legal differences in AI deployment

- Guidance for hybrid learning programs with participants from multiple regions
- Mechanisms for collaboration with partner universities on AI governance
- Guidance for navigating differences in cultural ontologies on AI use

4. Governance & Continuous Improvement

Does your institution have systems for ongoing AI governance?

- Defined roles and responsibilities for AI governance
- Data privacy and protection measures aligned with national and international regulations
- Staff and student training programs on AI ethics and responsible AI use
- Mechanisms for reporting AI-related issues or misconduct
- Processes for continuous review and updating of AI policies
- AI governance integrated into strategic planning

5. Brochure Use & Interpretation

As an instrument for self-assessment, the brochure is meant to encourage reflection and policy development. This process is best accomplished by involving a diverse group of stakeholders.

Part 2: AI use involves various risks, if you have checked many items, this indicates widespread AI adoption. This would require further examination and likely demands policies to mitigate ethical, operational, and legal exposures. Mapping these uses and conducting a detailed risk assessment is recommended

On the other hand, if you have checked very few items, this indicates limited AI adoption, and therefore likely limited AI-related risks. However, you may also want to consider strategic risks associated with non-AI adoption, in particular those associated with innovation and future skills development.

Part 3 & 4: If you have left many items unchecked, you may want to consider these for policy improvement or development. If you have checked many items, this indicates your institutional policies are developing toward or have achieved a more mature, ethical, and reflexive AI integration.

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